

NEWS

1

A warm welcome to our new partner project!

We are very happy to announce that the E-VOLVE Cluster family grew with yet another partner. The project ENLIGHTEN joined our Cluster in August. [Read more about their inspiring work!](#) Also, don't forget to click on all the links we added to get as much information as possible!

2

All about: Past Events from our partner projects

There was a lot going on in the last few months. Partners attended several events and were busy pushing their research on various channels. Find out more on page 2!

3

News from the projects

Our project partners have been very busy pushing their research forward. Be sure you don't miss anything that happened in the last few months.

Past Project Meetings

4

Coming Up

5

All about: Past Events

The European Researchers' Night is one of the biggest research events that takes place in about 400 metropolises in Europe. Austria's edition took place in Graz last September under the motto "Life is Science".

Representing their projects and also the E-VOLVE Cluster was SmartCorners.

Kids could explore and interact with demonstrators of smart corner systems (SCS).

Be sure you check out [more impressions from the event here!](#)

Members of [EGVIafor2Zero](#) gathered in Munich for a two-day meeting that combined strategic discussions, networking, and project updates. One part of the event was the presentation of the 2Zero project clusters, among others our E-VOLVE Cluster.

Read everything about it [here!](#)

HEFT attended the Coiltech®, International Coil Winding Exhibition & Conference Italy 2025 in Pordenone. [Fernando Garramiola](#) had the opportunity to present their latest research in magnet extraction from PMSM. Similarly, Javier Poza presented the optimization of PM motor with recycled magnets, carried out in the project.

Don't miss the [latest information about the HEFT project!](#)

We are looking back to the [EARPA-European Automotive Research Partners Association](#) Form Forum 2025, taking place in Brussels, end of September. [Medina Ćustić](#) and [Brandstätter Bernhard](#) from [Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH](#) represented the [E-VOLVE Cluster](#) at the event. VOLT CAR was also present, you can [read more here](#).

Here is [more from the event](#).

News from the projects

Just a few days ago, it was time for EM-TECH to celebrate. Project Partner Traxial successfully developed a next generation axial flux motor prototype. Get all the information [here!](#)

There is a new publication out! The partner projects Minded, Multi-Moby, EFFEREST and SmartCorners were mentioned in the “Research and innovation in smart mobility in Europe”. Read the [full publication here!](#)

For the SAE World Congress the projects EM-TECH, HEFT, MAXIMA, VOLT CAR and CliMAFlux joined forces.

Target of this paper was to introduce a family of European projects, all following the target of high efficiency and low-cost electric motors for circularity and low use of rare resources.

Click here to [get to the publication!](#)

SmartCorners, EM-TECH and HighScope were presented in a joint effort at the 38th International Electric Vehicle Symposium & Exhibition (EVS38).

Get all the information [here!](#) And be sure you don't miss the [full paper](#) as well as the [poster!](#)

Past Project General Assemblies

On the 18th and 19th of June ClIMAFLUX held their third Consortium Meeting. The event took place in Florence, Italy, and was hosted on the grounds of the academic partner, Università degli Studi di Firenze (UNIFI).

Read more about the event [here!](#)

EM-TECH's project general assembly took place in Kortrijk, Belgium at the beginning of July.

Watch a short video with photos from the meeting [here!](#)

Driving Innovation was the motto of the last SmartCorners General Assembly taking place at the premises of project partner Elaphe Propulsion Technologies Ltd. in Ljubljana last July. Simultaneously, HighScape's general Assembly took place at Elaphe.

The event also included a press conference giving EM-TECH, SmartCorners and HighScape the opportunity to share their latest research.

Find out more about the event and watch some videos we made on the [SmartCorners' website](#). You can read (and watch) even more about what has happened on EM-TECH's and HighScape's [posts](#).

Upcoming Meetings and Conferences

Upcoming Events		Project Webinars
 21.11.2025, 28.11.2025, 5.12.2025 and 12.12.2025 online		
 19.11.2025, 26.11.2025, 03.12.2025 and 10.12.2025 online		

The E-VOLVE Cluster Evolution

From the Achilles project, starting the E-VOLVE Cluster together with the founding projects in 2018, we are expressing our thanks to all project partners and projects contributing with their expertise to the European R&D landscape and collaborating in the E-VOLVE cluster.

